

Moral licensing, identity and eco-leadership: Can public managers' support for a green recovery be undermined?

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Abstract

We examined the possible effects of compensatory (i.e., 'economy vs. environment') messages on public managers' attitudes towards 'business-as-usual' plans, as opposed to green recovery plans, in the aftermath of COVID-19 pandemic. We devised a model tested with 90 Basque public managers. Exposing managers to compensatory messages increased support for green recovery plans due to an unintended moral licensing reduction effect. Municipal eco-leadership perception influenced the relationship between exposure to the compensatory message and the moral licensing reported by public managers.

Impact

Local public managers are increasingly involved in policy co-design, especially in the aftermath of COVID-19 pandemic. Municipal top management can benefit from our research by understanding how public managers' policy priorities are shaped by their own and leaders' goals in local administration. Specifically, we provide a model clarifying the role of managers' environmental self-identity and municipal eco-leadership in policy decisions that imply a trade-off between economic growth and the environment.

Keywords: public managers; moral licensing; COVID-19; reactance; green recovery

1. Introduction

Measures to stop the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic have confined workers to their homes, reduced transport, and altered consumption patterns. As a consequence of halting everyday activity, daily global CO₂ emissions decreased 17% on average by April 2020 compared to the previous year (Le Quéré et al., 2020). These kind of events are often exploited to resurface the problematic ‘economy vs. environment’ debate (Scorese, 2010) to oppose more ambitious environmental policies in favour of ‘business-as-usual’ practices (i.e., no significant change in policymakers’ attitudes toward the environment so that normal circumstances remain unchanged and sustain economic growth). Consequently, news reports linking environmental progress to the damage COVID-19 caused to the economy have proliferated and they could threaten post-pandemic green recovery plans by conveying the message that the environment has already benefited enough at the expense of the economic downturn (Ecker et al., 2020). Public managers who embrace this kind of message might conclude that economic growth should now be stimulated as rapidly as possible—regardless of the environmental cost. Importantly, such conclusions could shape COVID-19 policy responses because public managers are increasingly being considered as policy co-designers (Zaki & George, 2021). Previous research does not provide systematic knowledge about whether ‘economy vs. environment’ messages are able to influence public managers’ policy priorities. However, given that post-pandemic economic recovery is a unique opportunity to secure a transition to a greener economy (Lahcen et al., 2020), we deem it necessary to experimentally test the effect of these messages while we are still on the path to react to them.

Specifically, we address the following research question: How do ‘economy vs. environment’ compensatory messages change public managers’ attitudes toward a green recovery? We use the term ‘compensatory’ because these messages aim to convey the

problematic idea that the economy should be recompensed due to individuals' behaviour during lockdown that has favoured the environment. To highlight that the choice of the recovery plan is not an impartial decision, our study frames economic growth and environmental progress as a trade-off. Even though studies on policy choices have confronted emphasis on economic growth with both equity (Stokan et al., 2021) and the environment (Krause et al., 2016; Lubell et al., 2009), we concealed fairness (equity) considerations in the survey to make public managers choose between two openly partial policy options (i.e., economy vs. environment). While the environment ostensibly benefited from the disruption generated by COVID-19, the impact of the pandemic on equity is less evident and more abstract.

The present research builds on studies about similar environmental progress events in the last decade and broadly accepted theories from individual and organizational behaviour. By doing so, we explored the intersection of public management with other disciplines to better research the complexities of COVID-19 impact on administrations (O'Flynn, 2021). Studies focusing on the behavioural outcomes of climate wins have found that these achievements were followed by a reduction in individuals' pro-environmental attitudes (Gifford & Comeau, 2011; Hart & Nisbet, 2012; Hornsey & Fielding, 2016), which suggests that environmental progress might be generating moral licensing (i.e., the feeling of allowing oneself to deviate from moral or ideal behaviour in the future due to past good actions signalling an already sufficient contribution; see, e.g., Jordan et al., 2011; Merritt et al., 2010; Miller and Effron, 2010). In the environmental domain, being informed about recent environmental progress might permit individuals to engage in more self-indulgent behaviours since moral licensing feelings liberate them from the moral obligation of providing any additional environmental contributions (Truelove et al., 2016).

These messages could, however, cause an opposite effect as well: Following psychological reactance theory (Brehm, 1966), public managers could resist prioritizing a business-as-usual economic recovery if they perceive communication campaigns are trying to induce them to do so by suggesting they are entitled to moral licensing (Dillard & Shen, 2005). If the compensatory message is too obvious (i.e., clearly provides a one-sided view of the current situation), managers could feel manipulated and refuse to follow messages framing current environment progress as justification for focusing on stimulating economic growth. Also, some studies have shown (e.g., Truelove et al., 2014) that experiences of moral licensing compete with the desire of individuals to be consistent (Bem, 1972) and avoid cognitive dissonance (Festinger, 1957), proposing that past actions further reinforce behaviours in the same direction (Cialdini & Goldstein, 2004). Finally, determining the behavioural outcome of individual and organizational pro-environmental commitment is not straightforward and can lead to heterogeneous results, as suggested by self-regulation theory (Fishbach et al., 2009) and organizational agent–principal relationships (Shapiro, 2005).

Drawing on the above-mentioned literature streams, this study devises a behavioural model and examines the effect of a compensatory message on Spanish public managers' behaviour. We empirically test whether managers feel entitled to overlook more ambitious environmental plans in favour of stimulating economic growth or, conversely, whether the message garners support for a pro-environmental recovery plan. The latter would be considered a positive behavioural spillover or consistency behaviour, while the former is a negative behavioural spillover, called moral licensing (Galizzi & Whitmarsh, 2019). Our aim is to explore whether and under what conditions both kinds of behavioural spillover might occur as well as the role of individual and organizational environmental attitudes in promoting or offsetting them.

Although there is rich literature on behavioural spillovers in private decision-making that could at least guide our research (Dolan & Galizzi, 2015; Gholamzadehmir et al., 2019; Poortinga et al., 2013; Steinhorst et al., 2015), it would be inadequate to directly infer that what is true for private individuals also holds at the organizational level. We cannot ignore that private individuals' actions pursue individual goals, while public managers are acting on behalf of an organization when they make decisions. Therefore, managers cannot simply consider their individual goals when determining whether new information about environmental progress 'allows' them to change their priorities. Necessarily, managers will have to integrate their principal's (i.e., head of the local government) objectives in their own course of action (Schillemans, 2013), which opens an unexplored dimension in behavioural spillover research.

2. Theoretical framework

This study focuses on how external pressures, in the form of compensatory messages, influence strategic decisions of policymakers. Therefore, it falls within the scope of behavioural public strategy, which is "particularly interested in the micro-level of strategic decision-making in public organizations and networks (i.e., the actual people making strategic decisions)" (George, 2020, p. 4). The micro-level mechanisms of public strategy (i.e., the influence of specific stimulus in public managers' minds and behaviour) are important because they influence meso-level decisions (e.g., type of strategic plan actually adopted) and public service performance (George, 2020). Behavioural public strategy thus seeks to improve strategic public management and its impact on public service performance (George, 2020). While strategic public management is very broad, by including strategy formulation and implementation, and continuous strategic learning (Bryson & George, 2020), we focus on how politicians and managers respond to external

pressures when choosing between two specific strategies involving two different conceptualizations of public value.

From a behavioural public strategy perspective, this study identifies the possible behavioural outcomes of COVID-19 news and anticipates the trade-offs in public managers' values (i.e., economic growth vs. environment) before they happen and influence policymakers' strategic decisions (Sancino et al., 2021). Our research deals with “the core aspects of behavioural public strategy – namely its focus on (1) theories from behavioural science, (2) policymakers and (3) strategic decision-making” (George, 2020, p. 4). Regarding behavioural science theories, we depart from psychological reactance theory (Brehm, 1966) and draw parallels between self-regulation theory (Fishbach & Dhar, 2005) and principal-agent theories (Eisenhardt, 1989; Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Shapiro, 2005) to infer public managers' attitudes from studies on private individuals' behaviour.

Reactance theory (Brehm, 1966) posits that non-assertive messages assure recipients they are free to adopt a behaviour, while assertive messages threaten their freedom to choose, causing psychological reactance (Quick & Consideine, 2008). When recipients perceive that assertively phrased persuasion—as the compensatory message in the present study—is trying to influence a specific response from them, they ignore the recommended behaviour (Dillard & Shen, 2005; Kronrod et al., 2012) even if such behaviour contributes to a goal that is meaningful to them. Recent research shows that assertive environmental messages aiming to favour environmental priorities cause psychological reactance among individuals (Kavvouris et al., 2020; Liang et al., 2018). We question whether messages prioritizing the economy at any (environmental) cost can also cause the same negative reaction toward economic goals in public managers.

According to self-regulation theory (Fishbach & Dhar, 2005), past behaviour does not convey the same information for all individuals: If individuals interpret their behaviour as progress toward a goal, they will feel allowed to pursue other opposing goals (Fishbach et al., 2009). However, the same action can also be construed as goal commitment, which promotes consistency by providing information to individuals regarding the value of the goal for them. When past behaviour informs individuals about their goal commitment, their motivational resources continue to be used toward pursuing their initial goal; meanwhile, when individual's behaviour conveys information about their goal progress, motivational resources can be directed towards other complementary goals the individual wants to pursue as well (Mullen & Monin, 2016).

Self-regulation theory has been extensively supported by empirical findings (Fishbach et al., 2009; Sachdeva et al., 2009; Susewind & Hoelzl, 2014), showing that individuals focused on goal commitment tend to reinforce their past actions through consistency behaviour (i.e., a positive spillover), while individuals focused on goal progress tend to deviate from past behaviour, thus exhibiting moral licensing. The present research builds on these findings based on the dynamics of moral self-regulation and examines whether they could be transferred to the public management domain.

Given that the integrative approach of Self-regulation theory broadens the behavioural spillover literature (Susewind & Hoelzl, 2014), it is a useful framework to address our research question. Nevertheless, to the best of our knowledge, there are only a few studies (Carrico et al., 2018; Truelove et al., 2016) that consider past behaviour interpretation (i.e., commitment vs. progress) as a key determinant of pro-environmental spillover. These studies are confined to individual consumer decisions (as opposed to organizational decisions), which raises the question of whether the spillover predictions

of self-regulation theory still hold when the actor decides on behalf of somebody else, as in the case with public managers (Shapiro, 2005).

The relationship between public managers and their principals is often modelled on principal-agent frameworks (e.g., Boon, 2018). Agency theory focuses on the regulation of competing interests between two self-serving actors (Bendor et al., 2001; Eisenhardt, 1989). If agents (i.e., managers) are not controlled, they will bring their own interests to the job, which could collide with their principal's goals (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). This approach resembles the goal-progress mindset of self-regulation theory, in which the conflict between opposing goals requires oneself monitoring to control that one does not deviate and pursue a different self-serving goal (Fishbach et al., 2009).

Agency theory has been criticised for focusing on a conflictual perspective and neglecting other accountability dimensions (Schillemans, 2013). As an alternative to agency theory, stewardship theory emphasizes the shared goals and norms between principals and stewards (Davis et al., 1997; Dicke, 2002). When managers act as stewards of an organization, they are intrinsically motivated to pursue their principal's goals (Boon, 2018). Not only are stewards motivated by content-related values (e.g., delivering a public good), but also by ego-related values such as self-realization and feelings of belonging (Davis et al., 1997).

Stewardship theory alters the perspective on the relationship between the principal and the agent (Schillemans, 2013). The perspective change from conflicting goals to value-driven goals entails the same contrast present in self-regulation theory between having a goal progress mindset and a goal commitment mindset. Such similarities suggest that the mindset with which public managers interpret their course of action could be framed by the nature of their relationship with their principal: Agency theory views public managers' and their principal's interests as competing self-serving goals (Van Slyke,

2006). This is in line with a goal progress mindset prone to lead to moral licensing. On the contrary, in stewardship theory, there is no such conflict of interest between the agent and their principal. Public managers regard their values as aligned with those of their principal and do not need to self-regulate to pursue opposing goals (Schillemans, 2013). This resembles the reason why individuals with a commitment mindset generally do not need to deviate from their goal. Stewardship is thus conceptually similar to having a commitment mindset in that it promotes consistency behaviour and decreases the likelihood of moral licencing.

If these parallels between the agent–principal relationship and self-regulation mindsets are ignored, environmental communication campaigns targeting public managers will continue to be designed as if managers do not frame their past behaviour based on their relationship with their principal. Consequently, unless managers’ relationships with their principals are identified and leveraged in favour of the message, the behavioural outcome of communication campaigns targeting them will remain uncertain.

3. Model proposed

Our approach to disentangling the effect of the compensatory message on public managers’ selection of a pro-environmental plan integrates theories based on individual and organizational behaviour. We address the indirect effect of the compensatory message by drawing on psychological reactance theory to explore its influence on moral licensing (H1 and H2). We use consistency theory to explain the message’s direct effect on plan selection (H3). Self-regulation theory and agency theory will contribute to connecting predictions on public managers’ decisions across individual and organizational behaviour, respectively, in order to address the moderating effect of

environmental self-identity (H4a) and municipal eco-leadership (H4b) on pro-environmental plan selection, as illustrated in Figure 1.

(Insert Figure 1 here)

3.1. Compensatory message and moral licensing

News reports about environmental achievements linked to the COVID-19 pandemic have been widespread. Therefore, we consider it realistic to assume that all managers have the information and justification necessary to exhibit moral licensing (Merritt et al., 2010). Our object of inquiry is the specific effect of targeted compensatory messages aiming to reinforce the organic moral licensing reaction that managers may naturally experience in the after the pandemic. In this research, we will refer to compensatory messages as news in which environmental progress is framed as confronting economic growth, suggesting that, following an economic contraction linked to environmental progress (i.e., COVID-19 scenario), the economy should be recompensed.

Intuition could lead to the belief that a compensatory message could achieve its purpose of increasing moral licensing. However, moral licensing is a subtle phenomenon (Mullen & Monin, 2016), and trying to generate such by openly weighing the environment and the economy against each other could be too obvious to be effective. Following psychological reactance theory (Brehm, 1966), interested parties trying to change or control managers' current attitudes or behaviour may be perceived as a threat to their individual agency (Dillard & Shen, 2005; Quick & Consideine, 2008). Assertively phrased persuasion could backfire and motivate the message recipients to re-establish their threatened autonomy by resisting the recommended behaviour (Kim et al., 2017). Reactance is common in environmental communication when messages are too assertive (Kavvouris et al., 2020; Liang et al., 2018); this then casts doubt on the potential of the

COVID-19 compensatory message to generate moral licensing. Therefore, we tentatively propose the following:

H1: Exposing public managers to a COVID-19 compensatory message comparing economic and environmental achievements decreases their reported moral licensing.

3.2. Moral licensing reduction and pro-environmental plan selection

Moral licensing (Jordan et al., 2011; Merritt et al., 2010; Miller & Effron, 2010) refers to when a prior good deed provides a ‘license’ that allows one to exhibit morally questionable behaviour later on. This can be used as a pervasive weapon against the environment. Previous experiences show that progress toward emissions reduction in the last decade was followed by individuals feeling less motivated and reducing their effort to address climate change (Gifford and Comeau, 2011; Hart and Nisbet, 2012; Hornsey and Fielding, 2016). These findings are in line with studies showing that a boost in moral licensing diminishes environmental attitudes, e.g., residents increasing their electricity consumption after being told they have managed to reduce their water use (Tiefenbeck et al., 2013).

On the other hand, studies showing potential moral licensing as reduced by exogenous (e.g., framing) or endogenous (e.g., strong environmental values) factors have found that behaving pro-environmentally in one’s past can still generate a strong consistency behaviour when moral licensing triggers are deactivated (Gholamzadehmir et al., 2019; Meijers et al., 2019). Based on these findings, we hypothesize that the reduction in the organic moral licensing caused by manager’s reactance to the compensatory message will have a positive influence on public managers’ likelihood to choose a pro-environmental recovery plan after the COVID-19 pandemic:

H2: The decrease in public managers’ moral licensing experienced as an outcome of the compensatory message increases public managers’ likelihood of selecting a pro-environmental plan.

3.3. Direct effect of the compensatory message on pro-environmental plan selection

Still, the relationship between public managers being exposed to the compensatory message and choosing a pro-environmental plan cannot be explained by a reduction in moral licensing alone. By highlighting the environmental and economic outcomes of the pandemic, the compensatory message makes salient the past behaviours that caused such effects (e.g., transport and consumption reduction). When individuals are made aware of the fact they have prioritized the environment over economic growth in the past, their willingness to be consistent with past behaviour and their avoidance of cognitive dissonance (Festinger, 1957) could make them prioritize the environment once again. This support for a pro-environmental plan would not be related to moral licensing in this way but with the psychological desire to be consistent (Bem, 1972).

It has been shown that past behaviours reinforce subsequent actions in the same direction (Cialdini & Goldstein, 2004; Cialdini et al., 1995). Therefore, information provision about individual's past positive pro-environmental behaviour makes further pro-environmental behaviour and goals salient. This prompting serves as a silent reminder that can encourage public managers to behave pro-environmentally (Sussman & Gifford, 2012). This implies that, apart from the indirect effect via moral licensing reduction, the message itself can have an unrelated direct effect on public managers' pro-environmental plan selection. Therefore, we propose the following:

H3: In addition to its indirect effect mediated by moral licensing, the compensatory message also exerts a direct and positive influence on public managers' pro-environmental plan selection.

3.4. Moderating effects of individual and organizational commitments to climate governance

Kronrod et al. (2012) found that assertive messages cause most reactance when the target behaviour is important for the recipient of the message. This finding suggests that the level of reduction in moral licensing caused by the compensatory message may depend on the individual level of environmental commitment of public managers (Steg & de Groot, 2019). Following self-regulation theory, managers who are personally committed to the environment may construe COVID-19-related environmental achievement as commitment towards their goals. Such construal can trigger high reactance to the compensatory message and reduce managers' likelihood of suffering from moral licensing. In contrast, low individual pro-environmental involvement may lead to managers construing COVID-19-related environmental achievement as progress towards a goal. This could cause weak or no reactance to the compensatory message, facilitating moral licensing.

Therefore, public managers with strong (weak) individual biospheric values form robust (fragile) environmental self-identities (Van der Werff et al., 2013a) that could make them react strongly (weakly) against the compensatory message (Van der Werff et al., 2014). Consequently, we argue that the moral licensing reported by managers will depend on their environmental self-identity: High environmental self-identity is likely to help retain motivational resources toward managers' initial pro-environmental goals—even after they learn about recent progress in the fight against climate change—thus reducing moral licensing (Meijers et al., 2019; Mullen & Monin, 2016). This leads to the following hypothesis:

H4a: The effect of the compensatory message on moral licensing is positively moderated by public managers' environmental self-identity.

In the context of this research (public managers working for an organization), the intention to support pro-environmental plans may have organisational reasons because public managers also identify with principal's goals due to organizational identification (Miao et al., 2019). Firstly, stewardship theory suggests that the level of closeness in the relationship between principals and public managers could lead to managers acting as stewards. Secondly, according to agency theory, closeness facilitates local public managers to be properly stimulated and motivated by principals, which again indicates their potential to pursue organizational goals (Shapiro, 2005). Therefore, we can expect that the higher the pro-environmental commitment of leaders in a local government, the stronger the reactance of public managers to the compensatory message—in the form of moral licensing reduction. Municipal eco-leadership conceptualizes the principal's commitment to pro-environmental goals. This concept captures the presence of highly influential directors who enthusiastically promote sustainability in a local government (Barrutia & Echebarria, 2019). Therefore, we propose the following:

H4b: The effect of the compensatory message on moral licensing is positively moderated by public managers' perceived municipal eco-leadership.

4. Method

4.1 Sample

Public managers from the Basque Country region in Spain were contacted via email and asked to respond to an online questionnaire developed using Qualtrics software. The questionnaire was sent to 150 municipalities on 1 October 2020, and we obtained 102 responses from 30 different municipalities within a week. All participants responded successfully to the attention check included in the survey, but twelve participants were removed from the analysis because they did not complete the questionnaire in full. The

remaining 90 public managers who successfully completed the study comprised 81.2% civil servants and 18.8% politicians; participants were 45.6% male, 48.9% female, and 5.6% preferred not to reveal their gender; and their age ranged from 29 to 63 years ($M = 47.75$ years). The survey included an embedded experiment in which participants were randomly assigned to one of two conditions via a between-subjects design: (1) the experimental group ($n = 46$) or (2) the control group ($n = 44$).

4.2 Measurement and procedure

Public managers were asked to imagine themselves taking part in a working group that had the mandate to coordinate a response to the COVID-19 crisis. The scenario consisted of choosing between two post-pandemic recovery plans. Before choosing, the control group was not given any additional information, while the experimental group was told that *‘During lockdown months, CO₂ emissions decreased by 17% on average. According to a scientific study, there has been an unprecedented improvement in air quality: Environmental quality levels have improved but at the cost of halting economic activity and rising unemployment.’*

Thereafter, both the experimental and control groups were asked to choose the plan they would support: They could select either the business-as-usual plan focused on the economy (*‘Employment reactivation plan: 4% increase in employment—This plan prioritizes job creation and business development’*) or the pro-environmental plan (*‘Sustainable recovery plan: 2% increase in employment—This plan prioritizes sustainability and the reduction of CO₂ emissions’*).

Participants were then asked whether they would approve prioritizing the economy over the environment given the current situation. This question was used as a proxy for perceived moral licensing and it is an adaptation of a ‘moral self-image’ concept used in previous studies (Cornelissen et al., 2013; Khan & Dhar, 2006), but focused on

municipalities instead of on individuals. The environmental values held by the public managers themselves were measured using a two-item environmental self-identity scale (Van der Werff et al., 2013b, 2014), while their principals' environmental goals were measured using a two-item municipal eco-leadership scale (Barrutia & Echebarria, 2019). All items in Table 1 were rated using Likert-type scales with scores between 1 (completely disagree) and 7 (completely agree), and a Cronbach's alpha confirmed the reliability of the multi-item scales. The questionnaire was finalized after being pretested with several public managers from Basque municipalities, and all measures were then tested again with university students.

Psychological reactance was measured in a pilot study with university students using a four-item scale ($\alpha = .896$) from Dillard and Shen (2005), which included questions like '*The message tried to make a decision for me*' and '*The message tried to manipulate me*'. We found that those who received the compensatory message reported higher levels of reactance than those who received a more neutral message ($t[48] = -2.61, p = .038$). We did not measure the level of reactance in the main study with the public managers because including these questions would have made them suspect the purpose of the experiment. We argue that, if students inexperienced in management were able to note the manipulative character of the compensatory message, experienced public managers could perceive the manipulative intention of the message even more. Following open science best practices, we disclose the materials, dataset, code and output related to this research project. These files are available as an Open Science Framework (OSF) permanent archive at:

https://osf.io/8vgba/?view_only=afe75f63fc144976a27a4e6603c14f18

5. Results

The 46 public managers who received the compensatory message reported significantly less moral licensing ($M = 3.74$, $SD = 1.72$) than the 44 public managers in the control group ($M = 4.68$, $SD = 1.61$) ($t[88] = 2.682$, $p = .009$). The Cohen's d results showed a moderate effect size (Cohen, 1988): $d = .566$, 95% CI [0.142, 0.986]. The message's manipulation, which highlighted the compensatory relationship between the economy and the environment, reduced moral licensing, confirming H1. Besides, we identified a significant negative relationship between the compensatory message and moral licensing ($r = -.28$, $p < .01$), providing additional support for H1. The correlation analysis also shows a negative relationship between public managers' reported moral licensing and the selection of the pro-environmental plan ($r = -.48$, $p < .001$).

While only the 50% of public managers in the control group chose the pro-environmental plan, that percentage rose to 80.43% in the experimental group. Overall, the pro-environmental plan was the preferred option in our experiment, with 59 out of 90 public managers supporting it. We carried out a chi-square test of independence to examine the relationship between being exposed to the compensatory message and selecting the pro-environmental plan. The association between these variables was significant ($\chi^2[1, N = 90] = 9.23$, $p = .002$), indicating that participants who received the compensatory message were more likely than the control group to choose the pro-environmental recovery plan. The analysis of the effect size showed that the Cramer's Phi was $\phi = .320$, indicating a medium effect size (Cohen, 1988).

As part of the mediation analysis conducted with PROCESS Model 4 to test H2, the regression showed that the effect of the compensatory message on moral licensing ($b = -0.94$, $SE = 0.35$, $t = -2.68$, $p = .009$) and the effect of moral licensing on choosing the environmental recovery plan—when introduced together with the compensatory

message—were both negative and significant ($b = -0.71$, $SE = 0.19$, $t = -3.68$, $p < .001$). The mediation analysis confirmed a significant indirect effect of the compensatory message on the selection of the pro-environmental plan as mediated by moral licensing reduction ($b_{\text{indirect}} = 0.67$, $SE = 0.36$, 95% Boot CI [0.16, 1.57]). Apart from this indirect effect, there was also a remaining direct effect of exposure to the compensatory message on the pro-environmental plan selection ($b_{\text{direct}} = 1.09$, $SE = 0.53$, $z = 2.05$, $p = .041$). These direct and indirect effects, expressed in log-odds metrics, can be formulated as odds ratios ($e^{\log \text{ odds}} = \text{odds ratio}$) to facilitate their interpretation: The direct effect of the compensatory message increased the odds of choosing the environmental recovery plan by 2.98, and the indirect effect (via moral licensing reduction) further increased the odds by 1.95, thus confirming H3 and H2, respectively.

Using PROCESS Model 7 from Hayes (2017), we tested whether the indirect effect of the compensatory message on pro-environmental plan choice as mediated by moral licensing was moderated by municipal eco-leadership. The estimation of the moderated mediation index supported the significance of the proposed moderated mediation (10,000 bootstrap samples) since zero was absent from the bootstrap confidence interval ($b_{\text{modmed_eco-leadership}} = 0.58$, $SE = 0.23$, 95% Boot CI [0.18, 1.08]). Moderated regression analysis confirmed that the effect of the compensatory message on moral licensing was significantly moderated by the public managers' perception of municipal eco-leadership ($b_{\text{env. message} \times \text{eco-leadership}} = -0.82$, $SE = 0.26$, $t = -3.18$, $p = .0021$), providing support for H4b (Figure 2). Additionally, we included environmental self-identity as a moderator in the same moderated mediation model to test H4a. However, the moderated mediation index of environmental self-identity was not significant ($b_{\text{modmed_self-identity}} = 0.33$, $SE = 0.43$, 95% Boot CI [-0.29, 1.42]). We found no evidence to validate H4a, because the moderated regression analysis revealed that the effect of the

compensatory message on moral licensing was not significantly moderated by public managers' environmental self-identity ($b_{\text{env. message} \times \text{self-identity}} = -0.46$, $SE = 0.39$, $t = -1.19$, $p = .2363$).

(Insert Figure 2 here)

The results showed that the indirect effect of the compensatory message via mediator moral licensing was more strongly moderated by perceived municipal eco-leadership than by environmental self-identity. By computing the pattern of the conditional moderation effect on the mediator moral licensing, we found that the compensatory message only reduced public managers' moral licensing significantly at mean (M) and high (+1SD) levels of municipal eco-leadership. The conditional effect found on moral licensing indicated the increased likelihood of public managers choosing the pro-environmental plan, with managers who perceived medium and high levels of municipal eco-leadership being more likely to select it (See Table 2). This relationship was found to be significant at medium and high levels of eco-leadership—except when environmental self-identity was low, in which case, the effect was not significant. Municipal eco-leadership was thus found to be the dominant moderator that influences the size of the conditional indirect effect, confirming H4b.

Despite municipal eco-leadership being the main moderator of the indirect relationship between the compensatory message and choosing the pro-environmental plan, environmental self-identity was accountable for small variations in this relationship. Take, for example, the likelihood of the pro-environmental plan being chosen among public managers reporting high municipal eco-leadership (+1 SD). Although the indirect effect of the compensatory message on the members of this subgroup increases the chances of selecting the pro-environmental plan, the likelihood is higher for those with a strong environmental self-identity ($b = 1.70$) than for those with a weak environmental

self-identity ($b = 1.13$). This suggests that individual commitment towards environmental values makes a separate contribution to the selection of the pro-environmental plan. Overall, the moderating role of environmental self-identity was not as prominent as that of municipal eco-leadership, but it still was found to play a role in reinforcing the positive effect of high and medium municipal eco-leadership.

6. Discussion

6.1 Contribution and theoretical implications

We found that public managers exposed to an ‘economy vs. environment’ compensatory message were more likely to reinforce their commitment to the environmental goals of their organization by selecting a pro-environmental recovery plan to address the COVID-19 crisis. Our results corroborate that being exposed to a compensatory message causes a consistency spillover in future pro-environmental decisions by reducing the effect of moral licensing. We showed that, in situations like the COVID-19 crisis, in which moral licensing behaviour is already more prominent, trying to purposefully induce such behaviour is counterproductive. This is an interesting finding because the real effect of compensatory messages seems to be contrary to intuition and their original purpose.

The commitment-related moral licensing reduction found in our experiment is consistent with previous studies based on self-regulation theory (Schwabe et al., 2018; Susewind & Hoelzl, 2014), but it is also a consequence of the survey using assertive language when trying to influence a manager’s decision. The identification of moral licensing reduction in public managers is in line with findings highlighting decision framing (Truelove et al., 2014) and psychological reactance (Kavvouris et al., 2020) as factors deterring deviation from past pro-environmental behaviour.

However, not all the findings of studies conducted at an individual level may be directly transferred to an organizational level. In particular, public managers' propensity to reduce moral licensing and select the pro-environmental plan depended more on their perception of their principal's environmental values than their individual environmental self-identity. The higher the managers' perceived municipal eco-leadership, the stronger the effect of the compensatory message on moral licensing reduction and on managers' likelihood to choose the pro-environmental plan.

The strong influence of municipal eco-leadership on moral licensing reduction suggests that the source of positive spillover is not individual goals but the goals shared by influential superiors in local government. This principal–manager relationship model is congruent with stewardship behaviour in public administration (Schillemans, 2013) as well as with agency theory when public managers are properly supervised and motivated (Shapiro, 2005). Both approaches are plausible in close personal contact contexts like local governments.

In summary, compensatory messages framing recent news about CO2 emission reduction due to COVID-19 did not shift managers' priorities towards economic goals that neglect the environment. Even if compensatory messages were designed to be explicit, they did not make public managers feel entitled to cause more pollution to recover from the economic crisis generated by COVID-19 as fast as possible. The contrary effect seems to be more likely: When asked, public managers in the Spanish municipalities were prone to support a green recovery from the COVID-19 crisis. This answer was influenced mainly by the managers' perceptions of their principals' environmental goals.

Some public management studies have examined the effect of external pressures from interest groups on the strategic or policy choices of local governments. Previous

research has focused on land-use policy or, more specifically, on how municipalities respond to pressures for economic growth (e.g., builders and developers) versus environment protection (e.g., pro-environmental organizations) (Krause et al., 2016). Interestingly, the effect of external pressures depended on government political institutions (i.e., whether governments are led by elected politicians or professional managers). Most of these studies tended to attach predetermined roles to actors (Sharp et al., 2011). Consequently, elected politicians have often been viewed as involved in policymaking and influenced by external pressures, and professional managers as involved in implementing policy and focused on technical aspects (Zhang & Feiock, 2009). However, these predetermined roles have been considered inaccurate by authors that see professional managers as increasingly engaged in providing guidance in goal setting and working collaboratively with politicians in policy-initiating and policy-making teams (Svara, 2006).

The present research builds on behavioural public administration, which focuses on the micro-perspective of individuals. Therefore, our subjects are not supposed to play predefined roles (George, 2020). We provided them with a stimulus and observe how they responded to it. As usual in behavioural public administration, we use insights from psychology and behavioural economics (James et al., 2017). This study is thus illustrative of how micro-level behavioural strategic research can complement meso-level research to improve our understanding of policymakers' strategic choices.

6.2 Managerial implications

By identifying the linkages between a compensatory message highlighting past pro-environmental behaviour and managers' subsequent decision-making, we demonstrated that public managers do not make decisions in 'behavioural silos' (Dolan & Galizzi, 2015). Compensatory messages aiming to induce moral licensing by framing COVID-19

crisis recovery as a trade-off between the economy and the environment are unlikely to succeed in influencing public managers toward prioritizing a post-pandemic recovery plan. Instead, campaigners should be aware of the risks of using too obvious compensatory messages that could cause psychological reactance.

Based on the strong influence municipal eco-leadership was found to have on reducing moral licensing, we conclude that public managers behave either as stewards of their organization or as well-supervised and -incentivized agents. In either case, the public managers from our sample were motivated to pursue their principal's goals. However, an important nuance in this finding should be noted: When managers had low environmental self-identity (vs. medium or high), salient municipal eco-leadership did not seem to be sufficient to influence their selection of the pro-environmental plan. Unless the mismatch between a low environmental self-identity and a high municipal eco-leadership is addressed, the potential to leverage eco-leadership in favour of managers' pro-environmental behaviour will be wasted. Therefore, apart from promoting municipal eco-leadership, local governments aiming to ensure manager's pro-environmental behaviour will also need to increase their managers' personal identification with organizational goals through training and awareness (e.g., Miao et al., 2019). Nevertheless, municipal leaders should realize that, the wider the gap between leaders' and managers' pro-environmental values, the less receptive public managers will be to organizations' environmental goals. Encouragingly, research shows that defining organization's choice of strategic positions better and aligning the organizational structures more with these strategic positions could help principals to increase public managers' receptiveness to organizational goals (Jacobsen & Johnsen, 2020).

Our research has unveiled a behavioural model of public managers in Spanish local governments. This model suggests that successful environmental communication

requires both an organizational culture that motivates managers to pursue their principals' goals as well as principals whose strong commitment to environmental goals are transmitted. If municipal eco-leadership is communicated and embedded in the organization, public managers will be less likely to license and instead more prone to continue making pro-environmental decisions—even if they are not avid environmentalists themselves.

6.3 Limitations and directions for future research

Well-designed public policies can induce a green transition in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic (Lahcen et al., 2020), but such decisions must overcome bias in human judgement (Klenert et al., 2020). Our contribution seeks to enrich the post-pandemic research agenda by highlighting the behavioural ramifications that the awareness and past actions of public managers have. However, some limitations of this study should be noted, with timing being the most prominent. We decided to conduct our study at a very specific time point of the pandemic when COVID-19 cases were steadily increasing, as it was the beginning of the second wave in Europe. In the absence of a longitudinal study, it is unclear whether our intervention message would have caused a different effect on public managers during different points of the pandemic. Future studies could examine how moral licensing effects in principal-agent relationships vary depending on principals' and agents' characteristics, as politicians might behave differently from the rest of the personnel. Such analysis was beyond the scope of the present study but scholars pursuing this promising research avenue should note the need of larger and more heterogeneous sample sizes (less than 20% of managers in our sample were politicians) to conduct sufficiently powered studies on this matter, especially for moderation and mediation analyses.

Although a direct replication of our findings is unfeasible due to changing boundary conditions (e.g., timing, public concern and news coverage of environmental issues), further studies could explore the degree of generalization of the current research. For empirical generalizations using the same measurements and analysis with different populations, we refer interested readers to the OSF page of this research project. These files can be adapted or used as a reference to pursue similar research purposes, like testing and comparing the moral licensing effect of different compensatory messages. Empirical generalizations of this kind are in the best interests of public management research as they not only assess the moral licensing phenomena in another context but also test the consistency of these results over time. Moreover, our results can inform a priori power analyses of broader generalizations and extensions of the present research. We found a medium effect size (Cohen, 1988) when comparing moral licensing differences between groups of public managers, consistent with existing meta-analytic effect size estimations for private individuals' behaviour (Blanken et al., 2015).

The evidence presented supporting the idea that public managers in local governments are committed to principals' environmental goals offers a promising foundation for future research. Public management scholars interested in climate change can benefit from interdisciplinary approaches such as behavioural spillover research to explore how specific framings and communication campaigns trigger managers' moral licensing or behavioural consistency reactions (Dolan & Galizzi, 2015; Pollitt, 2015). Further research could examine how environmental stewardship behaviour can be induced among public managers in different decision-making contexts such as at higher levels of government that have a more hierarchical relationship between the principal and the agent. To achieve this, it would be useful to start by acknowledging the link between public management and behavioural sciences, as this could lead to new lenses through

which to look at long-standing challenges in the promotion of pro-environmental behaviour.

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Table 1. Item wording, sample statistics, and convergent validity.

<i>Construct and item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Dev.</i>	<i>Alpha</i>
Moral licensing <i>I would not disapprove/reprove, given the economic circumstances, that the municipality prioritizes economic measures over environmental ones</i>	4.20	1.72	-
Environmental self-identity (<i>Van der Werff et al., 2014</i>) <i>I am the type of person who acts in an environmentally friendly way</i> <i>I see myself as an environmentally friendly person</i>	5.44	0.88	.935
Municipal Eco-Leadership (<i>Barrutia & Echebarria, 2019</i>) <i>Relevant people in this municipality have expressed strong convictions toward sustainability</i> <i>Influential people in this municipality have enthusiastically promoted sustainability</i>	3.64	1.31	.915

Table 2. Conditional effect of the compensatory message on moral licensing and pro-environmental plan selection at different moderator values

<u>Moderator values (Low, mean and high)</u>		<u>Conditional effect on moral licensing</u>		<u>Conditional indirect effect on environmental plan selection</u>		
<u>Municipal eco- leadership</u>	<u>Environmental self-identity</u>	<u>Conditional effect</u>	<u>t</u>	<u>Cond. Ind. effect</u>	<u>Boot LLCI</u>	<u>Boot ULCI</u>
2.33 (-1 SD)	4.56 (-1 SD)	0.5395	0.97	-0.3807	-1.4590	0.5333
2.33 (-1 SD)	5.44 (M)	0.1334	0.28	-0.0941	-0.7887	0.8602
2.33 (-1 SD)	6.32 (+1 SD)	-0.2727	-0.45	0.1925	-0.6833	1.7281
3.64 (M)	4.56 (-1 SD)	-0.5296	-1.12	0.3738	-0.6240	1.3498
3.64 (M)	5.44 (M)	-0.9357	-2.85**	0.6603	0.1755	1.4970
3.64 (M)	6.32 (+1 SD)	-1.3418	-2.84**	0.9469	0.2759	2.3340
4.96 (+1 SD)	4.56 (-1 SD)	-1.5988	-2.63*	1.1282	-0.0960	2.4662
4.96 (+1 SD)	5.44 (M)	-2.0049	4.26***	1.4148	0.6549	2.6148
4.96 (+1 SD)	6.32 (+1 SD)	-2.4110	4.36***	1.7014	0.8622	3.2325

Note. *p < 0.05; **p < 0.01; ***p < 0.001.

Figure 1. Theoretical Model.

Figure 2. The effect of the compensatory message on moral licensing, moderated by municipal eco-leadership

Note. High municipal eco-leadership (+1SD) = 2.33; mean municipal eco-leadership (M) = 3.64; low municipal eco-leadership (-1SD) = 4.96. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.